

DIFFUSION OF AGROFORESTRY INNOVATIONS IN ODEDA AREA OF OGUN STATE, NIGERIA: IMPLICATIONS FOR EXTENSION SERVICES

Adeyanju Agbelemoge¹ and Oladapo Akinyemi²

¹Dept. of Agricultural Extension and Rural Sociology College of Agricultural Sciences, Olabisi Onabanjo University, Ayetoro Nigeria, ²Federal College of Forestry, Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria, Ibadan, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

There is always a conflict between agricultural and forestry sub-sectors over the use of land. Agroforestry systems offer a solution to such conflicts in that it is a land arrangement system that accommodates both production of food crops and forest products on the same piece of land. Agroforestry practices could be adopted by farmers in Nigeria for increased production of food and fibres. This study therefore sets out to examine how these innovations were diffused and adopted in Odeda Area of Ogun State, Nigeria. A survey was carried out using ten out of the nineteen major communities in the Local Government Area by balloting. An interview schedule was administered on randomly sampled two hundred farmers. The data obtained were analyzed using descriptive statistics and test of hypotheses was done with chi-square (X^2) analysis. Farmers had low literacy level, they were relatively old in age and were obtaining very low income from farming operations. The adoption score was very low and no economic gains were indicated. The factors identified as responsible for the low adoption score were education, economic status, types of agroforestry systems and sources of information on agroforestry innovations. The findings of this study could be used to draw attention to the need for an aggressive agricultural extension programme to promote agroforestry practices among farmers.

KEYWORDS: Diffusion, Agroforestry, Innovations, Implications, extension service

INTRODUCTION

Food crisis, declining forest resources and environmental imbalance are the problems of wide spread concern in Nigeria today. The agricultural production system in most developing countries of the world has deteriorated due to inability to produce enough food for their teeming population coupled with the demands for rapid industrialization and urbanization (Anon, 1991).

The concentration of population is particularly high in the Southern Nigeria where the tropical rainforest abounds. In their natural efforts to increase agricultural productivity, Nigerian farmers have been involved in de-reservation of the constituted forest reserves and deforestation of free areas for farming purposes. This has led to environmental degradation and diminished forest resources.

The incompatibility of agricultural and forestry land uses has contributed immensely to low production of food and forest products in Nigeria. However, there is no land management system that accommodates the production of foods and forest products on the same piece of land other than Agroforestry.

Concept of Agroforestry

Agroforestry seeks not only to re-align the two major land use sub-sectors (agriculture and forestry) with revamped output per unit area but also offers alternative development strategies for rural areas (Adeyoju, 1981). This is achieved through integration of woody perennials (trees, shrubs, palms etc.) on the same piece of land with herbaceous plants and/or animals either in spatial arrangement or in time sequence and in which there are both ecological and economic interactions between the tree and non-tree components.

The definition accepted by International Council for Research in Agroforestry (ICRAF) states that "Agroforestry is a collective term for system and technologies of land use where perennials, woody plants (trees, bushes, shrubs and, by assimilation bamboos) are deliberately cultivated on ground otherwise used for

crops and/or stock rearing in a spatial or temporal arrangement, and where there are interactions both ecological and economic between the woody plants and other perennial components of the system”.

It is a land use system that enables the farm to remain productive throughout the year, resist plagues and infestations that monoculture can cause, and minimize soil erosion. The micro-climate within the farm is modified and minerals are re-cycled through natural processes that include nutritious fruits, forage, fuel wood, construction pole, timber, resins, etc. This diversity of product makes the farmers more self-sufficient and it protects him from the market fluctuations which are disastrous to small scale farmers producing one kind of product. Wood products have also the great advantage that they can be kept when market price is low without losing their values.

Classification of Agroforestry Systems

There are only three basic sets of components that are managed by man namely woody perennials, herbaceous plants and animals in agro-forestry land use systems (Nair, 1985). However, ICRAF distinguishes four major systems.

- (1) Agro-silviculture system (i.e.) trees and crops
- (2) Silvo-pastoral systems: (i.e.) trees and livestock
- (3) Agrosilvipastoral systems: (i.e.) trees, crops and livestock
- (4) Other systems (e.g. aquaforestry i.e. fish production with trees, apiculture: bees raising with trees; sericulture: i.e. silk production with trees.

There are further classifications of agroforestry systems based on various criteria such as systems structure, functions, socio-economic scale and level of management and ecological spread (Nair, 1987).

- (5) Silvicultural basis – Based on the composition of the components including spatial admixture of the woody components, vertical stratification of the component mixture and temporal arrangements of the different components.
- (6) Functional basis – Based on the major function or role of the system, mainly of the woody components, (those that can be productive (e.g. food, fodder, fuel wood and so on or protective (e.g. windbreak, a shelter belt, soil conservation, and so on).
- (7) Socio-economic basis–Based on the level of inputs of management (low input) or intensity or scale of management and commercial goals (subsistence, commercial, intermediate).
- (8) Ecological basis – Based on the environmental condition and ecological suitability of the system, on the assumption that certain types of the systems are more common in or appropriate for certain ecological conditions.

The various agroforestry practices in Nigeria, according to Adegbehin and Igboanugo (1990) include:

1. Shifting cultivation
2. Traditional homestead farm or garden
3. The taungya system
4. The alley cropping/farming systems
5. The scattered farm trees with multipurpose objectives
6. The shelterbelt/live fences
7. The silvopastoral systems
8. The silvi-fisheries (aquaforestry)

Theoretical Framework

One important process through which systematic social change takes place in rural areas is the adoption of innovation by farmers (Jibowo, 1992). The adoption process is the mental process through which an individual passes from first hearing about the new idea to its final adoption (Rogers, 1962; Jibowo, 1992).

The rate at which new farm practices are adopted according to Jibowo (1992), depends on some variables and these include:

- (1) Innovation related factors e.g. cost, complexity, utility and group action, innovation process.
- (2) Farmer related factors e.g. Age, Education, Farm size, Income, Access to credit facilities, Participation in organization, Use of Mass Media, Source of Farm Information.

- (3) Change Agent related factors (e.g. frequency of contact with farmers, professional competence, human relation skill, knowledge of extension workers, and positive attitude towards extension work, motivation and commitment).
- (4) Community – related factors (e.g. The history of cooperation or conflict, availability of natural resources such as weather, vegetation, soil fertility status, presence of perennial streams, political homogeneity, ethnic homogeneity, community identification, presence of infrastructural facilities like pipe-borne water, electricity supply, feeder and motorable roads).
- (5) Institutional factors (e.g. discernible decision – making process, credit facilities, cooperative organization and land tenure).

Research Problems

One of the greatest problems militating against abundant production of food, fibres and forest products is the land tenure system. Moreover, the conflict between the agricultural and forestry sub-sectors over the use of land cannot be resolved without the adoption of agroforestry practices. However, significant increase in food and forest resource through agroforestry systems can only be attained if the relevant innovations flow effectively from the sources to the farmers. Most research activities on agroforestry were concentrated on technical improvement aspects of the system (Chris, *et al*, 1994) while there were no systematic studies on diffusion, adoption and the other extension aspects of the system.

Agroforestry is a problem-solving system in both the rural and urban environments. Hence, the practice of Agroforestry should aim at serving the needs of the people. Therefore this study is necessary for the development of result-oriented approach towards farmers` adoption of agroforestry innovations.

Objectives of the study

The objectives of the study are to investigate the diffusion and adoption of agro forestry innovations in the study area and specifically focused on:

- i. Socio-cultural and economic status of the farmers.
- ii. Types of agroforestry innovations disseminated and adopted.
- iii. Sources of farm information.

Hypotheses of the study

The hypotheses of the study were set up in the null form as:

Ho₁ There is no significant relationship between the socio-cultural and economic status of farmers and adoption of agroforestry innovations.

Ho₂ There is no significant relationship between the type of agroforestry innovations disseminated and level of adoption of the innovations.

Ho₃ There is no significant relationship between the source of farm information and the adoption of agroforestry innovations.

METHODOLOGY

The data were collected from ten communities out of the nineteen major settlements in Odeda Local Government Area of Ogun State, Nigeria using balloting system. A random sampling technique was used to select interviewees, twenty male farmers from each community on which a structured interview schedule was administered by three enumerators (A village extension agent, a forest officer and one of the researchers.)The research instrument was validated and pretested to twenty respondents in a non participating community (Elenusonso) near National Institute of Horticultural Research and Training (NIHORT) Ibadan.Descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, means and ranking were used in describing the data while inferential statistics were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance to determine the association between key variables and farmers` adoption of agroforestry innovation using chi-square (X^2) analysis and coefficient of contingency (c).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Personal and Socio–economic Characteristics of the Farmers;

Two hundred male farmers were interviewed and used for the study. With regards to age, 50% of them were between 51-70 years old, and 6% were more than 70 years. Only 13% were between 31 to 40 years old while 8 farmers (4%) were less than 30 year. As age is an important factor of adoption and in most cases having negative relationship according to Akinola (1986) and Adekoya and Ajayi (2000). Most of the farmers were married except for only six single males probably those farmers below 30years of age.

Educational Background

Only 16% of the farmers had secondary education or above, most farmers (61%) completed only primary education and 23% had no formal education at all. This can affect adoption adversely since education has a positive relationship with adoption of innovations as reported by Akinola (1986). Farmers were 56% Christians and 40% Muslims with few (4%) traditionalists.

Land Acquisition Methods and Farm Size

Most (70%) farmers in the study area were inheritors of the land they use while acquisition through forest officers rated 2nd with only 14%. Rent and Leasehold were next with 11% and 5% respectively. This should enhance adoption since inheritance will give holders total power to use their land. The size of holding was between 2 to 4 hectares for 71% of the farmers. Only two farmers had more than 4 hectares while others (28%) had just 2 hectares. On the average, land holding size was about 2.8 hectares. This average hectarage is sufficient for some types of agroforestry innovations.

Table.1. Personal and Socio-economic characteristics of the Farmers

Age of farmers	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Below 30 yrs	8	4
31-40	26	13
41-50	54	27
51-60	70	35
61-70	30	15
70 & above	12	6
Educational background		
No formal education	46	23
Completed pry school	122	61
Completed modern school	18	9
Completed secondary school	9	4.5
Any other	5	2.5
Religion		
Christianity	122	56
Muslim	80	40
Traditionalist	8	4
Hectarage		
2 Hectares	56	28
2.1-4.0 Hectares	142	71
4.1- 6.0 Hectares	2	1
Land tenure system		
First occupancy	4	2
Inheritance	136	68
Rent	22	11
Leasehold	10	5
Forest officers	28	14
Farmers contact with VEA		
Very frequent (fortnightly)	22	11
Frequently (monthly)	40	20
Occasionally	42	21
Not at all	96	48

Maize and cassava ranked first with all farmers (100%) planting them followed by cocoyam with 57% of farmers and yam with 54% farmers, rice ranked last with only 9% of farmers planting it. Kola ranked first among the tree/cash crops with 17% farmers, followed by cocoa with 11% of the farmers while the last was oil palm tree with only one percent of farmers. These crops can perfectly fit into agroforestry system if farmers are ready to adopt agroforestry innovations.

Animals Domesticated by the Farmers

Domestic fowl ranked first with 43% of farmers, followed by goat with 21% farmers, sheep and pig were last with 6% of farmers and 2% of farmers respectively. As many as 28% of farmers did not keep animals at all. Since agroforestry involves rearing of animals these should be a positive factor of adoption of agroforestry innovations

Sources of Information on Agroforestry Innovation

All farmers received their information on agro-forestry innovations either through radio (80%) or forest workers (19%). Most farmers (52%) had contact with Agricultural Extension Agents either frequently or occasionally. Only two farmers (1%) received agroforestry innovations from Agricultural Extension Agents. No farmer sought information through printed materials, contact farmers nor Non-Governmental Organization (NGOs). This may probably be due to low level of education of the farmers; the radio being the major source of information to farmers may affect adoption adversely since farmers cannot ask questions on clumsy areas but will prefer to abandon such innovations for lack of clarity.

Table 2: Economic status of farmers

Crops grown		Frequency	Percent (%)			
Maize		200	100			
Cassava		200	100			
Cocoyam		114	57			
Yam		109	54.5			
Rice		18	0.9			
Cash crops						
Kola		33	16.5			
Cocoa		22	11			
Oil palm		02	01			
Animals						
Fowls		86	43			
Goats		42	21			
Shop		12	06			
Pig		04	02			
Annual income	Tree component		Agric crops		Animals	
	Freq.	Percent (%)	Freq	Percent (%)	Freq.	Percent (%)
<5000	21	10.5	-	-	48	24
5001-10000	5	2.5	-	-	59	57.6
10001-15000	-	-	56	26	37	18.5
15001-20000	-	-	112	56	-	-
Above 20000	-	-	32	16	-	-

Participation in Tree Planting and Conservation

Only 46 farmers (23%) planted trees in their farmlands while only 52 farmers (26%) conserved trees when they come across them on their farmlands. it was due to lack of knowledge on agroforestry innovations and the benefits therein.

Out of 52 farmers (26%) that adopted agroforestry innovation, half of them 26 farmers were practising Taungya systems, 16 farmers (30%) were practising scattered farm trees with multiple purpose objective while 6 farmers (11%) and 4 farmers (8%) were practising homestead garden and living fences respectively. 148 farmers (74%) did not adopt any form of agroforestry innovation at all.

Incentive Received by Farmers on Tree Planting

Subsidized seedlings was the only incentive farmers received for planting trees on their farmland and it was to those practicing Taungya only. The lack of incentives may cause non adoption of agroforestry innovations.

Farmers Income from Farm Operations Annually

About 21 farmers (40%) of 52 that practised Agroforestry innovation realized less than N5, 000 annually from the tree components while 10% of farmers realized between N5,000 and N10,000. From animal components, 48 farmers (24% realized below N5,000 annually; 59 farmers (30%) realized between N5,000 and N10,000 annually while 37 (19%) farmers realized between N10,000 and N15,000. From agricultural crops component, 56 farmers (28%) realized between N10,000 and N15,000 each; 112 farmers (56%) realized between N15,000 and N20,000 while 32 farmers (16%) realized as high as over N20,000 each annually. All these farm incomes were too small and inadequate for a whole year.

Farmers Reasons for Adoption of Agroforestry Innovation

Out of the 52 farmers that adopted agroforestry innovations, 34 (65%) of adopters had reasons of food and traditional medicine. The remaining 18 farmers (35%) adopted for timber and demarcation of boundary purposes. Farmers were probably not aware of other benefits of agroforestry and this may be a reason for low adoption of agroforestry innovations.

Farmers Reasons for Non-adoption of Agroforestry Innovations

Lack of awareness of its success elsewhere ranked first followed by complexity of the innovations. The risk involved and high costs of input were subsequent reasons of non-adoption by farmers' perception. When farmers were not aware of the benefits they will not be expected to adopt as there were no visible gains. Secondly if prospective adopters do not understand the innovations or how to go about them there cannot be adoption.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis One

There is no significant relationship between the socio-cultural and economic status of farmers and adoption of agroforestry innovations. The results of the test revealed that two of the four socio-cultural and economic parameters were not significant at 0.05 levels. These were farmers' age and farm size. The significant ones were farmers' educational level and economic status at 0.33 and 0.30 coefficients of contingencies respectively.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant relationship between the type of agroforestry innovations disseminated and level of adoption of the innovation. This hypothesis was tested and found to be significant; its coefficient of contingency was 33%.

Hypothesis Three

There is no significant relationship between the sources of farm information and the adoption of agroforestry innovations. The third hypothesis was tested and found to be significant; the coefficient of contingency was 29%.

H ₀	Variables	Degree of freedom	X ² Value	Tabulated Value	Decision at 0.05 LS	C of C
1a	Age Vs Adoption	5	10.36	11.07	N.S	
b	Educational level vs Adoption	4	24.92	9.488	S.	0.33 (33%)
C	Farm size vs Adoption	2	1.37	5.991	N.S	
d	Economic Status vs Adoption	4	19.34	9.488	S.	0.30 (30%)
2	Type of Agroforestry vs. Adoption	3	24.34	7.815	S.	0.33 (33%)
3	Sources of information vs. Adoption	2	19.05	5.991	S.	0.29 (29%)

CONCLUSIONS

Only 52 farmers out of the 200 respondents adopted agroforestry innovations and the farmers adopted a single practice each. Moreso, there was little or no effort at dissemination of agroforestry innovations by any agency, not even the Forestry Department; and no incentives was given to attract farmers to adopt the innovations. Consequently, there were no tangible economic (financial) gains derived by those 26 farmers that adopted Taungya system except the seedlings that were freely distributed to them. The investigation revealed that they were forced out of their plots 3 – 4 years after planting; hence they could not realize any economic gains from the trees.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To substantially increase adoption of agroforestry innovations in the study area, the farmers have to be motivated both intrinsically and extrinsically using social, communal and economic gains to individual farmers as incentives.

The Agricultural Extension Service should increase its scope to include agroforestry under the Unified Agricultural Extension System (UAES) thereby intensifying the education of farmers in agroforestry innovations.

The gender specific concept of the Women in Agriculture Component should include Agroforestry in its scope and reach out to women and their children in the rural areas to educate them on the advantages of adopting agroforestry innovations.

A participatory technology development approach (PTD) which encourages farmers involvement in the development and evaluation of agroforestry techniques based on the knowledge and value system that exists in their community be promoted in agroforestry innovations. It will remove complexity and ensure adequate coverage of agroforestry needs of these communities.

The government should assist the Forestry Department to intensify efforts in the dissemination of agroforestry innovations using mass communication, audio-visual and mobile cinema materials and methods in the villages and communities. Incentives that can result into economic benefits to participating farmers (such as credit facilities, subsidized inputs like fertilizers, chemicals, subsidized equipment like cutlasses, hoes, sprayers, spades, shovels and head pans should be provided.

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Corresponding author

Adeyanju Agbelemoge

Dept. of Agricultural Extension and Rural Sociology College of Agricultural Sciences, Olabisi Onabanjo University, Ayetoro Nigeria.

E-mail; adeyanjuagbelemoge@yahoo.com